

The **first** trans-continental **Networking Academy** for African and European **Digital Innovation Hubs**.

6.1 Dissemination and Communication Plan – First version

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Glossary and Abbreviations

AI	Artificial Intelligence
CSO	Civil Society Organization
DIH	Digital Innovation Hub
EU	European Union
HPC	High- performance Computing
ICT	Information, Communication & Technology
KPIs	Key Performance Indicators
M	Month
MS	Microsoft
SEO	Search Engine Optimization
SMEs	Small – Medium Enterprises

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Executive Summary

This document aims to provide the AfriConEU consortium with an effective and efficient plan to follow in communicating and disseminating the work and results of the project. A separate document will describe how the exploitation of the results will be achieved (D6.14 and D6.15). The first version of this document includes a detailed dissemination and communication strategy. The upcoming versions (D6.2, D6.3 and D6.4) will update the strategy and report all the implemented dissemination and communication activities, including their effectiveness in reaching the dissemination and communication goals.

It is clarified in advance that even though the terms of communication, dissemination and exploitation are sometimes used as synonyms and overlap during the project's life cycle, they have different meanings and objectives. The above terms in this document are used according to the following definitions:

- Communication can be understood as informing, promoting, and communicating the project's actions and results to multiple audiences, including the media, the general public, and the project's stakeholders. Communication takes place from the beginning of the project until the end.
- Dissemination refers to the public disclosure of the project's results, especially to stakeholders that might use the results in their work. These stakeholders refer to authorities, industry, policymakers, sectors of interest and civil society. Dissemination takes place at any time and as soon as the project has results.
- Exploitation refers to the concrete use of the project's results for commercial, societal, and political purposes addressed to the industry, including SMEs, authorities, industrial authorities, policymakers, sectors of interest, and civil society. Exploitation takes place towards the end and beyond, as soon as the project has exploitable results.

This communication and dissemination plan was made at the beginning of the project, in March 2021 (Month 3). Updated versions are expected to be delivered in February 2022 (Month 13), May 2023 (Month 28), and January 2024 (Month 36). The updated versions will integrate a) additions by the work done during the implementation of AfriConEU and

b) suggestions after the review by the European Commission. The more the project proceeds, the more specific and complete this document becomes. Hence, this initial plan serves as a general guideline for the whole AfriConEU consortium, including the essential elements, such as target audiences, key messages, strategy, channels, tools, activities, actions expected by all partners.

It is clarified that this document is dedicated to the project's external communication. For the project's internal communication within the Consortium, the deliverable **D1.1 Management and Quality Plan** can be consulted.

1. Introduction

1.1 About AfriConEU: Distinctive traits

AfriConEU is a European project that supports the strengthening of existing Digital Innovation Hubs (DIHs) in Africa. It facilitates the collaboration between EU and African DIHs to strengthen a joint EU-Africa innovation and startup ecosystem.

What makes AfriConEU different from other relevant projects?

- AfriConEU will create the first Trans-continental Networking Academy for African and European Digital Innovation Hubs involving diverse partners and stakeholders from various industries.
- All the involved actors have unique competencies, experiences, and expertise from both continents, including Digital Innovation/ Tech hubs, Universities, Consultancies, Investment firms, Civil Society Organizations (CSOs).
- This collaboration between African and European partners will empower Digital Innovation Hubs at a local, national, continental, and trans-continental level and boost the digital economy.
- The project strengthens the EU-Africa partnership and shared agenda, reinforcing long-term collaboration with mutual benefits.

These novel and distinctive propositions have been taken into account to create a straightforward and standard narrative that can be used consistently throughout the project and adapted to different audiences. Part of that narrative is conveyed through the project's claim by creating the first Trans-continental Networking Academy for African and European Digital Innovation Hubs.

1.2 Target audiences and key messages

Identifying target audiences and the key messages to use with them is vital to maximizing the effectiveness of communications.

Audiences have been developed from within the AfriConEU stakeholders' group. Stakeholders can be defined as "any group or individual who can affect or is affected by the

achievement of an organization's purpose."

Before communicating and disseminating the project, it is essential to think about the stakeholders as audiences: Who are they? Where are they? What can AfriConEU offer them? Online research was made by the communication and dissemination partner to identify further the primary and secondary target groups and how social media could target each of them.

The primary target groups include Digital Innovation Hubs, Tech Hubs, Business Incubator Networks, Co-working Spaces, Accelerators, Local entrepreneurial and Startup community supporters, Entrepreneurs (with a focus on professionals, women, and marginalized youth), Digital entrepreneurs, Startups, SMEs, Young innovators, ICT professionals, Investors, Corporates, Mentors, Africa Diaspora Communities, Business angels, Venture funds and Foundations. The secondary target groups include Pan-African Networks of innovation stakeholders, Public officers/Policy stakeholders (incl. EU & AU), Local governments, Education and training organizations, and the General public.

The Consortium's partners are encouraged to tailor-make their communication and dissemination according to the target group they are most actively engaged/ working with. A detailed explanation is given for the target groups, social media, and the project's communication and dissemination goals in Table 1. It is clarified that the website, the press releases and the newsletters are targeting the general public and all the identified target groups.

Primary target groups

Table 1 - List of AfriConEU Primary Target Groups

Primary Target Group	Goal	Facebook	LinkedIn	Twitter	Instagram	YouTube
DIHs and ecosystem builders from both continents	Capacity building and networking by enlarging their network, allowing the project to get deeper into local ecosystems, and providing them with a Pan-African / European reach; these will also be key stakeholders to learn how to replicate AfriConEU Academy programs in the future; to attract them to enroll in the platform of DIHs to be part of this network.					
Tech hubs						
Business incubators networks						
Co-working spaces						
Accelerators						
Local entrepreneurial and Startup community supporter						
Entrepreneurs (with a focus on professionals, women, and marginalized youth)	International networking opportunities; better access to investors; and a more enforced innovation ecosystem. The Consortium aims to establish AfriConEU Online Community as a reference for entrepreneurs /startups when looking for support to internationalize, scale up, or find talents to hire; to involve them to be part of the Academy Network to gain knowledge, develop synergies, etc.					
Digital entrepreneurs						
Startups						
Digital startups						
SMEs						
Young innovators						
ICT professionals						
Investors	To exploit the most innovative technologies and business opportunities in Africa through investment and/or partnerships; They are expected to support the project by participating in the project activities and through eventual sponsorship enabling the sustainability of the Academy's programs.					
Corporates						
Mentors						
Africa diaspora Communities						
Business angels						
Venture funds						
Foundations						

Secondary target groups (Key influence groups/ multipliers):

Table 2 - List of AfriConEU Secondary Target Groups

Secondary Target Group	Goal	Facebook	LinkedIn	Twitter	Instagram	YouTube
Pan-African Networks of innovation stakeholders	To engage them in the project, and disseminate widely into their networks; to attract them for current and future collaboration.					
Public officers/Policy stakeholders (incl. EU & AU)						
Local governments						
Education and training organizations						
General public	Follow and share; spread the word and raise awareness.					

The target groups' successful engagement is crucial to the overall project's success and, most importantly, for building a robust EU-Africa Innovation and startup ecosystem. To this end, engaging with target groups will mean:

- Encouraging, facilitating, and supporting the participation of relevant stakeholders in AfriConEU Academy activities (locally implemented workshops, webinars, brokerage events, design thinking boot camps, masterclasses, and project-relevant training and networking activities);
- Motivating stakeholders to contribute to the project's activities through their experience, expertise, knowledge. They will provide meaningful input to project processes and outcomes (e.g., through the research activities, the co-design of the Academy programs, and the evaluation tasks);
- Allowing stakeholders to benefit from and use the project outcomes.

The different communication and dissemination activities will be designed considering the various actors of the project and considering the relations, processes, and technologies within AfriConEU. The communication and dissemination strategy will be oriented not only towards the target groups but especially towards the project's *momentus*, being continuously adapted and updated, as follows:

Step 1: Raising awareness about AfriConEU and inviting the community to participate in

meaningful public discussions;

Step 2: Consolidating information about the AfriConEU networking academy;

Step 3: Inviting DIHs, SMEs, entrepreneurs to participate in the pilots;

Step 4: Decisive and timely communication about demonstration actions and pilots experience;

Step 5: Communication for the future of AfriConEU.

In its essence, communication will be a continuous process starting at the beginning of the project, involving showcasing the project's activities, outcomes, intermediate and final results. Dissemination will be the crucial element of the project's visibility and sustainability as well. Therefore, the dissemination activities are a focus area within the project's duration to promote the project's ideas, knowledge, results, and the completed project outcomes and their future exploitation.

2. Strategy, channels, and tools

2.1 Strategy Outline

AfriConEU's communication and dissemination activities are regarded not only as a way of informing society and stakeholders about the project but also to support its development. Therefore, all members are expected to contribute to the communication and dissemination efforts according to their capability.

The Consortium has established three main objectives:

- To raise the project's awareness among digital innovation-related stakeholders in the project's nine countries and other locations around Europe and Africa, supporting the work in other WPs.
- To share experiences and results - especially on the impact of the networking academy on the beneficiaries around Europe and Africa.
- To disseminate the respective project outcomes to the broadest possible community of potential beneficiaries.

Communication and dissemination will be implemented from the offset of the project, and a preliminary strategy has been developed. Different phases somehow overlap with each other

since communication and dissemination are a continuum.

2.1.1 Preparation (M1-4)

In this phase, a preparation for the smooth implementation of the communication and dissemination activities takes place. The project's website is being created, along with the visual identity, the social media channels, and the project's communication and dissemination toolkit. Different audiences are being identified and characterized to target the communication and dissemination efforts better. Templates for reporting on essential contacts and events or other dissemination activities undertaken by the partners are also being created.

2.1.2 Communication: raising the awareness of the AfriConEU project (M2-36)

Once the visuals and the strategic plan are ready, the communication starts with promoting the project's most significant aspects, such as the vision, objectives, name explanation, and the partners. The information is being communicated to the target audiences and the stakeholders at a regional, national and trans-continental level - special attention is being given to DIH and relevant networks. A separate communication strategy is being created to ensure smooth synergies' creation with relevant projects, networks, and initiatives in the Digital Innovation Hub ecosystem. The channels and tools primarily being used include the website, leaflet, social media, letterhead, pitch deck, press release, newsletter, synergies with other networks and projects, traditional media, and presentation of the third-party project events.

2.1.3 Dissemination: promoting project results among stakeholders (M3-36)

The objective is to promote results among selected stakeholders to support the adoption of the AfriConEU Logic model. The primary target audiences are the DIHs and individuals (entrepreneurs, startupper), and policymakers. The dissemination relies heavily on the partner's existing wide networks. Also, the project will implement scientific publications in peer-reviewed conferences and journals. The consortium is committed to widely disseminating the results. The channels and tools primarily used include event attendance, several social media campaign strategies to target, partners' networks, third-party events, and own events. Additionally, the project targets Digital Innovation conferences focusing on

Entrepreneurship, Innovation and Technology.

2.1.4 Exploitation and Sustainability (M23-36)

A dedicated exploitation and sustainability plan will be prepared and made available to the partners as a separate document by Month 25 (February 2023, D6.14) and then updated by Month 36 (January 2024, D6.15). The plan will collect all exploitable results, such as the Deployment Toolkits and capacity-building resources and set the targets, indicators, and milestones to ensure the project results' life after completing the project. The sustainability plan will offer an exit strategy that will present a well thought, effective route for continuing the project activities without public funding. It will also encourage the partners to utilize further the project's services and the knowledge produced in their organization activities. The partners are advised to identify critical results and deliverables with a high potential for exploitation and report to the responsible partner (INOVA+).

2.2 Communication Channels and Tools

2.2.1 Logo

AfriConEU logo was created using the project acronym as the main element and a number of circles and lines that form the shape of Africa's map (Figure 1). Since AfriConEU aspires to become the first Trans-continental Networking Academy for African and European DIHs, this is depicted with lines and circles connecting African countries, thereby representing a robust digital network. Thus, formal typography was selected and rounded for a softer effect. The EU is bold and deep blue, the same colour with the dots to depict the interaction and sharing of knowledge between the two continents. Blue is used as a base colour as it is associated with technology and innovation. Deep blue is used to indicate confidence, reliability, and responsibility. More information about the logo can be found in Annex 1 of this document.

Figure 1 - AfriConEU Logo

Name explanation

The AfriConEU name has a hybrid meaning. On the one side, it symbolizes the connection between Africa and Europe, in terms of the partnership, networking and digital innovation. On the other side, it also encapsulates the intention of this EU-funded project to support African startups, through the strengthening of Digital Innovation Hubs, to become the next Unicorns¹.

Project's motto or subtitle

The motto of the project is: "The first trans-continental Networking Academy for African and European Digital Innovation Hubs".

This motto is used to clearly convey the project's message and main aim. It is included in the majority of the produced project's visuals. By adding the motto, the reader/user can understand faster and easier the project's idea.

2.2.2 AfriConEU Pitch Deck

AfriConEU will be presented at several events, conferences meetings and other occasions to disseminate project developments and results, enhancing the overall dissemination efforts. For that reason, a pitch deck has been developed so all partners can use it to present the project on any occasion that may arise (Figure 2).

¹ Refers to any Startup that reaches the valuation of \$ 1 billion.

Figure 2 - AfriConEU Pitch Deck Slides' Sample

2.2.3 AfriConEU PowerPoint Template

The AfriConEU PowerPoint template (Figure 3) will be used to create relevant presentations during the project's participation in events, conferences, meetings, and other occasions to disseminate project developments and results, enhancing the overall dissemination efforts. A presentation template (PPT) has been designed in line with AfriConEU visual identity to strengthen the common AfriConEU identity. Additionally, as required per Article 29.41 of the Grant Agreement, all material used for communication and dissemination purposes of AfriConEU will demonstrate the EU emblem along with the statement that the project has received funding from the H2020 Research and Innovation programme.

Figure 3 - AfriConEU Presentation Template

2.2.4 Word Deliverable Template

The AfriConEU deliverable template was produced in line with the overall communication and dissemination material visual identity (Figure 4). The consortium partners will use it for the development of all project deliverables. The template has a cover page that displays the project's logo, its subtitle and the EU emblem, along with the statement that the project has received funding from the H2020 Research and Innovation programme. The following two pages include all the deliverable's information (number, full title, the work package number, and title) and the authors' information.

Figure 4 - AfriConEU Word Deliverable Template

2.2.5 Website

A web page is already up and running at <https://africoneu.eu/>. The website was released on Month 2 of the project – March 2021. It is intended to be the main point of information for anybody interested in the project. It will publish up-to-date information about the project and its activities, along with the deliverables.

The structure of the website is the following:

Home: This is the main entry point. It includes the project's vision, an invitation to the primary target groups to get in touch, along with the call to join the newsletter (Figure 5).

Figure 5 - AfriConEU website Home Page

Footer: The website applies a standard footer in all its pages, where someone can check the latest videos of the AfriConEU YouTube channel, the latest Instagram posts and the latest Tweets (Figure 6).

Figure 6 - AfriConEU Website Social Media Footer

Additionally, as required per Article 29.41 of the Grant Agreement, all material used for communication and dissemination purposes of AfriConEU will demonstrate the EU emblem

along with the statement that the project has received funding from the H2020 Research and Innovation programme and that this website reflects only the author's views and the Research Executive Agency or European Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains (Figure 7).

Figure 7 - AfriConEU Website EU disclaimer

About us: This section includes information about the project, solution, methodology, phases of the project, vision and objectives, partners, and the Advisory Board (Figure 8).

Figure 8 - AfriConEU Website About Us Page

Networking Academy: This section has preliminary information about the Networking Academy of AfriConEU and its three main categories: DIHs Capacity, Transcontinental partnership, AfriConEU Online Community (Figure 9).

Figure 9 - AfriConEU Website Networking Academy Page

Platforms: This section includes the Agrifood Cooperation platform by our partner ITC - Innovation Technology Cluster Murska Sobota, and the AfriConEU e-learning platform (Figure 10).

Figure 10 - AfriConEU Website Platforms Page

Join: This section includes a call for visitors to join AfriConEU depending on the category they belong (Figure 11).

Figure 11 - AfriConEU Website Join Page

Library: This section includes a gallery, scientific publications, training resources, and the public deliverables of AfriConEU (Figure 12).

Figure 12 - AfriConEU Website Library Page

What's New: Here, the user can find the Press Clips and the project's Newsletters (Figure 13).

This section will fulfil the functions of:

- providing updates on the project,
- publishing interesting and relevant content to generate engagement and,
- helping to boost the SEO concerning certain terms.

Figure 13 - AfriConEU Website What's New Page

This part of the website will host all the latest updates of the project related with participation in events, organization of activities including relevant information and visual material. Moreover, all press releases, press clips and newsletters will be uploaded in that section.

Contact Us: The section includes a contact form for interested users in receiving more information or contacting us (Figure 14).

Figure 14 - AfriConEU Website Contact us Page

The Privacy Policy, together with the Terms and Conditions, has been included in the AfriConEU website, set for the general rules and policies governing the visitors' use of the website.

2.2.6 Social Media

AfriConEU aims to have a strong presence in social media, enhancing its reach-out to target audiences and the general public. The partners use their existing networks in social media to communicate the project further and increase its reach to stakeholders and potential partners and beneficiaries. Special attention has been given to the custom use of each social media according to the specific target audiences.

According to the proposal description, the project has established (M4) social media accounts for Twitter, LinkedIn, Facebook, Instagram, and a YouTube Channel. All channels are monitored regularly, and changes are being adapted according to the audience's engagement and feedback. The project's identifier hashtag is **#AfriConEU**, accompanied by the secondary hashtags **#DIH**, **#H2020**, **#EUAfrica** and **#AfricaEurope** when needed. The number and type of hashtags change depending on the specific social media.

Social media are used to communicate and disseminate not only project-related information but also valuable content for the followers, such as up-to-date news, articles, available opportunities, podcasts, and motivational quotes. All the information goes along with the framework of the project and key areas, such as Digital Innovation, Entrepreneurship, Start-up ecosystem, Networking, Capacity-building, and Digital economy. All partners are expected to provide engaging content, links, or articles to the dissemination manager. The project will

use social media to support the engagement efforts of social innovation practitioners.

The project has a [Linktree account](#), including the social media accounts and a subscription form link to the Newsletter (Figure 15). The Linktree will include buttons and links promoting project-related events and opportunities.

Figure 15 - AfriConEU Linktree Page

2.2.6.1 Social media management tool

A social media management tool is being used to better strategize and execute the social media plan. This tool refers to one platform, in which all social media accounts and pages are managed, with the possibility of customizing each channel with the different information and material. It provides all the needed tools in one platform, and some of the significant features include Publishing & Scheduling, Interactions or Engagement, Content Creation & Media Library, Social Listening & Monitoring, Reporting & Analytics, and Team Collaboration. The tool provides instant access to brand mentions across social, news, blogs, forums, reviews, while it helps the project understand how its brand makes people really feel about sentiment analysis (positive, negative & neutral). It helps uncover trends and conversations of any keywords, hashtags and phrases across the web. The AfriConEU social media plan is being executed through a Publisher & Visual Calendar, in which the social media management team can cross-network social publish, edit, and filter, complete post customization per channel, while composing a new post.

2.2.6.2 Social media monthly analytics report

At the end of each month, the project receives a detailed analytics report that helps drive

strategic decisions, such as the best time to post, which hashtags perform better and in which area most of the followers are concentrated. The report refers to all the social media accounts and some of the provided information include profile summary, number of followers and mentions, analysis of each post, page views, impressions and engagement, audience’s demographics by geographic area, industry, company size and level of seniority, fans by country, city, age and gender and general reach. In combination with Google and Linktree analytics, the general strategy is being analysed and adapted to the numbers and conclusions from the monthly report.

2.2.6.3 Facebook page

The AfriConEU Facebook page serves primarily for communication with the general public (Figure 16). Secondly, it also communicates to local entrepreneurial and startup community supporters, entrepreneurs, young innovators, ICT professionals, mentors and African diaspora communities. A database is created with essential pages, which are tagged in the posts according to the content and relevance. Three posts per week are published on the Facebook page unless there is an urgent update or essential publication. In this case, more posts occur, either on separate days during the week or the same days as the scheduled posts (Monday - Wednesday - Friday). This initial strategy is subject to change during the project according to the feedback and data analysis performed to understand better what the audience prefers.

Figure 16 - AfriConEU Facebook Page

2.2.6.4 Twitter account

The AfriConEU Twitter account (Figure 17) serves for communication with some of the most significant project's stakeholders, including DIHs and ecosystem builders from both

continents, Tech hubs, Business incubators networks, Co-working spaces, Accelerators, Local entrepreneurial and startup community supporter, SMEs, Pan-African Networks of innovation stakeholders, Public officers/Policy stakeholders (incl. EU & AU), Local governments. Special attention is being given to reaching out to EU & AU instruments and stakeholders, engaging them in the project's updates and developments. The AfriConEU Twitter account functions as a platform to reinforce the dialogue between other relevant H2020 projects and initiatives in the same field, contributing to the joint EU-Africa partnership and agenda. A database is created with essential accounts, which are tagged in the posts according to the content and relevance. Every week (Monday - Tuesday - Wednesday - Thursday - Friday) five to ten tweets are published on the Twitter account and several retweets. While attending an event or when appropriate, the AfriConEU Twitter account will be used for live updates as well. This initial strategy is subject to change during the project according to the feedback and data analysis performed to understand better what the audience prefers.

Figure 17 - AfriConEU Twitter Account

2.2.6.5 LinkedIn page

The AfriConEU LinkedIn page (Figure 18) serves for communicating with some of the most significant project's stakeholders, including DIHs and ecosystem builders from both continents, Tech hubs, Business incubators networks, Co-working spaces, Accelerators, Local entrepreneurial and startup community supporter, startups, SMEs, Investors, Corporates, Mentors, Business angels, Venture funds, Foundations, Pan-African Networks of innovation stakeholders, Public officers/Policy stakeholders (incl. EU & AU) and Education and training

organizations. A database is created with essential pages, which are tagged in the posts according to the content and relevance. Every week five posts are published on the LinkedIn page unless there is an urgent update or essential publication. In this case, more posts occur during the same days as the scheduled posts (Monday - Tuesday - Wednesday - Thursday - Friday). This initial strategy is subject to change during the project according to the feedback and data analysis performed to understand better what the audience prefers.

Figure 18 - AfriConEU LinkedIn page

2.2.6.6 Instagram account

The AfriConEU Instagram account (Figure 19) serves for more personalized communication with entrepreneurs (focusing on professionals, women, and marginalized youth), Young innovators, ICT professionals, and mentors. Three different campaigns are being implemented on Instagram:

1. #MondayInsights, providing insightful information about digital innovation, entrepreneurship, business, and technology.
2. #LearnAboutAfriConEU, providing information about the project, its activities, results, etc.
3. #FridayMotivation, providing motivational quotes from successful entrepreneurs and experts worldwide.

A database is created with essential accounts, which are tagged in the posts according to the content and relevance. Three posts per week are published on Instagram unless there is an

urgent update or essential publication. In this case, more posts might occur, either on separate days during the week or the same days as the scheduled posts (Monday - Wednesday - Friday). This initial strategy is subject to change during the project according to the feedback and data analysis performed to understand better what the audience prefers.

Figure 19 - AfriConEU Instagram Account

2.2.6.7 YouTube channel

The AfriConEU YouTube channel (Figure 20) serves to communicate the project to all target audiences, providing simple, friendly, and modern videos. Apart from short videos with the project’s information, more interactive and animated videos will be created and published on the YouTube Channel during the second and third year of the project.

Figure 20 - AfriConEU YouTube Channel

2.2.7 Newsletter

Newsletters will be sent every six months to inform on the project's activities and progress, retaining the followers and stakeholders' interest. A tentative structure follows:

- Introduction: a quick recap of the past six months,

- Upcoming events,
- Interview with someone related to the project whose views can be interesting concerning the project's areas of interest,
- Published deliverables,
- A couple of helpful published articles published on the web (or good practices).

Ideally, the contents on the newsletter will link back to content on our website, driving traffic. The partners will send contributions for the newsletter to the dissemination managers at least two weeks before the launching date so that everything can be reviewed and placed into a proper template. Youthmakers Hub, as the communication and dissemination leading partner, will share the newsletter with the remaining partners, so it can be then also sent to their networks. The partners are kindly requested to send proof of this to Youthmakers Hub. A newsletter recipients' list has already been created and will be enriched constantly during the project implementation. Data Protection Laws will be fully respected. The newsletters' recipients will be asked to provide their consent before sending information related to the project. Special attention is paid to security and respect for the users' personal data privacy and confidentiality. Therefore, relevant activities and aspects regarding personal data will be fully compliant with the applicable national, European, and international legal framework and the European Union's General Data Protection Regulation 2016/6798. Interested parties will be able to subscribe and unsubscribe at any given point from the AfriConEU Newsletters. All the collected data will be stored and saved in the responsible partner's servers. These data will not be accessible by third parties.

To achieve a broader distribution and facilitate the engagement of as many stakeholders as possible, the AfriConEU partners will be encouraged to distribute the newsletters to their contacts interested in the project. A specific option for subscription to the newsletter recipients list has been included on the AfriConEU website (Figure 21) and Linktree account.

Figure 21 - Newsletter Subscription (call to action button-footer)

2.2.8 Leaflet

A project leaflet has been developed with key points about the project and relevant information, targeting the main audiences and general public (Figure 22). Apart from the English version, it is being translated into Greek, Italian, Portuguese and Slovenian (AfriConEU partners' official languages). There will be two formats for the leaflet, one for digital use and one printed for use at events and face-to-face distribution.

Figure 22 - AfriConEU Leaflet

2.2.9 Videos

The project will develop promotional videos for AfriConEU. The videos will combine recorded footage from the project and archive images. Roughly, the themes for the videos will be as follows: introduction to the project, explanation of the networking academy, activities, and summary of the project. The project will share the videos on the YouTube Channel and all

social media.

2.2.10 Press Releases

Nine press releases will be written and published during the project (one every four months). The press releases will include updates regarding the project's activities and progress. They will be written in English, but the partners are expected to translate them into their language and share them within the national level with media channels. The partners are invited to write more press releases if they wish to boost the project's visibility at their national level. The AfriConEU logo, the website address and the acknowledgment of EU funding should always be displayed. The communication and dissemination partner, Youthmakers Hub, is available to guide, clarify doubts and provide the necessary information and audiovisual material to all partners when needed.

We will make use of the dissemination opportunities offered by the European Commission: Horizon magazine, Research*EU and Cordis website.

2.3 Dissemination activities

2.3.1 Presentation of the project at third party events

The AfriConEU project and partners will participate in local, national, and international conferences, industrial fairs events, and exhibitions. The aim is to raise the project's awareness in terms of activities and, later on, to inform on possible collaboration opportunities, results and outcomes. The partners act as "AfriConEU ambassadors." They will focus on promoting AfriConEU in key industry events that attract a high number of players across the sectors of interest (Digital Innovation, AI, HPC, Cybersecurity Blockchain, etc.), aiming to maximize the effect of direct interaction with relevant stakeholders. Additionally, attending relevant events will also benefit AfriConEU by having continuous updates about specific business aspects to address AfriConEU exploitation plans.

Table 3 provides a list of indicative relevant upcoming events in which the presentation of AfriConEU will add value to the project's objectives. The indicated list will be constantly updated and further communicated with the AfriConEU partners to plan upcoming events.

The dissemination through these events will be customized based on AfriConEU's primary target audiences, ensuring wide dissemination across sectors and stakeholders.

Table 3 - List of AfriConEU relevant events & conferences

Month	Title	Location	Date
March	Driving Business in Africa	Online	16 March 2021
	The Future of Work in Africa	Online	16 March 2021
	IoT Forum Africa 2021	Online	25-26 March 2021
April	Emerging Valley	Online	07-08 April 2021
May	Digitalizing Africa	Online	04 May 2021
	Africa Tech Week	Online	05-06 May 2021
	Afrobytes	Online	25 May 2021
June	Women Tech Global Conference	Online	07 June 2021
	Africa Trade and Investment Convention	Amsterdam, Netherlands	11-12 June 2021
	Viva Technology	Paris, France & Online	16-19 June 2021
	Dublin Tech Summit	Online	17 June 2021
	9th Digital Africa Conference	Online	22 June 2021
	European Research & Innovation Days	Online	23-24 th June 2021
August	sSTARTUp Day 2021	Tartu, Estonia & Online	25-27 August 2021
September	Growth Marketing Summit 2021	Frankfurt, Germany	02 September 2021
	Africa Tech Summit	Nairobi, Kenya	14-15 September 2021
	SA Innovation Summit	Cape Town, South Africa & Online	21-23 September 2021
October	IoT Solutions World Congress	Barcelona, Spain	05 - 07 October 2021
November	Africa Tech	Cape Town, South Africa & Online	08 - 12 November 2021
	Global Entrepreneurship Congress	Online	14-17 November 2021
	IoT Tech Expo Europe 2021	Amsterdam, Netherlands	23-24 November 2021
December	EU - Africa Business Summit	Marrakech, Morocco	29-30 November 2021

2.3.2 Synergies with relevant initiatives, networks, and projects

Developing synergies and networking with relevant initiatives is one of the project's priorities. Such actions will enable AfriConEU to reach different target audiences more effectively.

Therefore, a precise strategy will be developed (Task 6.3). All opportunities for sharing and exchanging outcomes, resources, and knowledge will be identified and documented (D6.12 and D6.13). Partnerships will be a cornerstone of the project. They will lead to building sustainable connections between ecosystems in Africa and between Africa and Europe. A vital component of the project is identifying and liaising with existing networks and initiatives to support African startups, accelerate the digital transformation, and boost the digital economy. The AfriConEU Networking Academy services will be made available to support the above-described causes. Consequently, this task involves that partners will draw upon their insights in combination with desk-based research to identify the various relevant networks and initiatives in Africa and Europe. An initial plan to target relevant industries and networks includes:

- [AfriLabs](#)
- [The Africa-Europe Innovation Partnership](#)
- [DIHNET](#)
- [AUEU Youth Cooperation Hub](#)
- [DISRUPT AFRICA](#)

AfriConEU will strengthen the broader Africa-Europe partnership, developing the connections of the local players with the existing consortium networks. Ultimately, this task will connect the project formally with the key players in Africa's and Europe's digital innovation scenes.

3. Actions expected from the partners

All partners are expected to contribute to the communication and dissemination efforts. Most of the activities that are planned have been outlined in the previous pages. However, it is also in this section that the work distribution is outlined.

Before going into details, it is good to remember that all actions should refer to or include:

- The project's common visual identity: logo and standard manual (the needed files are available in the Microsoft Teams folder).
- The project Url: <https://africoneu.eu/>.

- Acknowledgment of EU public funding: "*This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101016687.*"
- The official EU logo (EU emblem can be found [here](#). The guidelines on how to use it can be found [here](#)).

3.1. Display AfriConEU on your institutional website

Please, write a text about the AfriConEU project and include it on your website (and share it on your social media). You could consult the already existing available texts on the AfriConEU website. The partners are kindly requested to send proof of this to Youthmakers Hub. You are also encouraged to write about relevant deliverables or milestones in your news section.

3.2. Stakeholder's database

Whenever partners make new contacts and links with networks interested in being part of the project, they should fill in the excel document created for that purpose and that it is available in the Microsoft Teams folder.

3.3. Contribution to the newsletter

The partners are invited to contribute to the newsletter content depending on the project's ongoing activities and tasks. They are expected to send relevant material to Youthmakers Hub to be published in the Newsletter, ideally two weeks before the launch date. This will help plan so that everything can be reviewed and placed into a proper template before sending. Youthmakers Hub will send the Newsletter to the contacts in the project database. All partners are expected to send it onto their contacts and send them to their contacts. The partners are kindly requested to send proof of this to Youthmakers Hub.

3.4 Partners' social media accounts

The partners are advised to post on their social media accounts whenever essential news on the project or a relevant milestone has been reached. They are expected to share the project's

press releases, videos, good practices, newsletters or deliverables. Also, they are expected to share any news on the project on local media. They are also encouraged to share articles on topics they consider to be related to the project. They are also highly encouraged to tag relevant partners and the AfriConEU social media accounts. All partners' social media accounts can be found in annex 3.

3.5 Press releases and media contacts

The partners are expected to translate press releases to their language (when needed) and send them to their contacts in the media. A proof of this should be sent to Youthmakers Hub. In case the partners decide to write their own press releases - if they wish to do so/consider it a good strategy to boost their actions - they should remember to include the AfriConEU logo, website, and the acknowledgment of EU funding. They are also expected to share any media features or articles on their social media accounts and send them to Youthmakers Hub for press clipping or adding them in the file shared in the Microsoft Teams folder.

3.6 Events

For each event that the partners organize or attend, they should use the project's visual materials (i.e., leaflets) and branding (project logo, color palette, and fonts). The events should be announced on the partners' website and social media (the partners should remember to tag @africoneu). Whenever possible/appropriate, the partners are encouraged to tweet during the event they are attending and communicate with Youthmakers Hub to send relevant information to be published from the AfriConEU Twitter account. Twitter is very strategic for the project's communication and dissemination objectives. The partners are highly advised to use it when appropriate. A template has been created to report events (it can be found in the Microsoft Teams folder) and at the end of this document in Annex 2. The partners should send the event report to Youthmakers Hub within two weeks after completing the event, accompanied by at least two pictures of high quality. There is also a file where the partners can list the events they are planning to attend in the Microsoft Teams folder.

In the framework of WP2 the first event of the project has been organized for 28th of April 2021. The event entitled as “Building Resilient African Digital Economies post-COVID – Focus on Ghana” will be an online roundtable discussion among leaders of Digital Innovation Hubs (tech hubs, universities, incubators, accelerators), entrepreneurs and entrepreneur support network leaders, digital skills providers and other innovation ecosystem actors (investors, investment enablers, policymakers and advocates). This virtual event will seek to understand how hubs can be better supported to help African economies harness the digital opportunities that are arising and to catalyse innovation on the continent.

4. Impact Measurement

The communication and dissemination efforts support the overall goals of the project. There are specific goals and objectives to be achieved for AfriConEU. Communication and dissemination activities should help achieve these goals, with particular attention given to Digital Innovation Hubs and Entrepreneurs' involvement. Therefore, metrics and indicators have been developed for the communication activities as presented in Table 4.

Table 4 - Communication & Dissemination Key Performance Indicators

Communication & Dissemination KPIs		
Tool Channels	KPIs	Expected Results
AfriConEU Website	Number of visits	1000 visits per month.
	Time spent on the web platform	> 40% of visitors spending 1 minute or more in the platform
	Returning visitors	More than 40% of returning visitors
Communication material	Number of items distributed	At least 1500 flyers distributed
	Number of contacts from stakeholders	At least 100 contacts showing interest in receiving AfriConEU promotion materials
Social media	Number of members and engagement	LinkedIn: At least 200 followers
		YouTube: at least 100 subscribers
		Twitter: 500 followers by end of M12 / 1000 followers by end of M28
		Instagram: 500 followers by end of M12 / 1000 followers by end of M28

Communication & Dissemination KPIs		
Tool Channels	KPIs	Expected Results
		Facebook: 200 followers by end of M12 / 500 followers by end of M28
		More than 40% of posts are shared
Press releases	Press list	1 press list with at least quarterly updates and press contacts from the African and European titles from the countries represented in the Consortium
	Number of press releases issued	At least 3 press releases issued by the project per year
	Clipping/publications coverage	At least 10 press clippings (articles) per year
	Media Interviews	At least 2 interviews per year
Newsletters	Number of subscribers	500 by end of M12 / 1000 by end of M24 / 1500 by end of M36
	Number of Newsletter issues	12 newsletter issues throughout the project's lifecycle
	Opening rate per newsletter	Average of at least 18% opening rate by end of M12/ 20% by end of M24 / 25% by end of M36

5. Planning

Table 5 presents the activities planned for the first semester of the project in what concerns the development of communication tools and the production of deliverables within WP6.

Table 5 - Planning first Semester

Planning first semester (February – July 2021)			
Activity	Deadline	Partner	Notes
Visual Identity	15 th April 2021	YMH	Delivered 3 rd March 2021
Website	15 th April 2021	YMH	Delivered 15 th March 2021
Setting of Social Media Account	15 th April 2021	YMH	Delivered 6 th March 2021
D6.1 Dissemination and Communication Plan – First version	15 th April 2021	YMH	Delivered 15 th April 2021
D6.5 Dissemination toolkit and project's website	15 th April 2021	YMH	Delivered 13 th April 2021
Pitch Deck	15 th April 2021	YMH	Delivered 29 th March 2021
Presentation Template	15 th April 2021	YMH	Delivered 29 th March 2021
E-mail Signature	15 th April 2021	YMH	Delivered 10 th March 2021

Planning first semester (February – July 2021)			
Activity	Deadline	Partner	Notes
Letterhead	15 th April 2021	YMH	Delivered 29 th March 2021
Word Deliverables Template	15 th April 2021	YMH	Delivered 5 th March 2021
Leaflet	15 th April 2021	YMH	Delivered 2 nd April 2021
Press Release 1	April 2021	YMH	It will be delivered 20 th April 2021
Newsletter 1	July 2021	YMH	It will be delivered 15 th July 2021

Annex 1: AfriConEU Logo and Visual Identity

The AfriConEU logo has been developed in all formats in RGB and CMYK colours. It exists in EPS, JPEG, PDF, and PNG formats and is uploaded in the Microsoft Teams folder shared with all partners. All information regarding the AfriConEU logo & visual identity has also been reported to the Standards Manual, part of the **Deliverable 6.5** shared with all partners. The AfriConEU logo was created using the project acronym as the main element and a number of circles and lines that form Africa's map. Since AfriConEU aspires to become the first Trans-continental Networking Academy for African and European DIHs this is depicted with lines and circles connecting African countries, thereby representing a robust digital network. Thus, formal typography was selected and rounded for a softer effect. The EU is bold and deep blue, the same colour with the dots to depict the interaction and sharing of knowledge between the two continents. Blue is used as a base colour as it is associated with technology and innovation. Deep blue is used to indicate confidence, reliability, and responsibility. White and black versions of the logo have been developed to be used over coloured backgrounds.

AfriConEU Colour Palette

RGB			
	0000CD	17174D	FFFFFF
CMYK			
	35469D	1D194C	FFFFFF

The colour palette above represents the colours used in designing the AfriConEU logo in RGB and CMYK colour modes. RGB colours are best suited for digital use (on screens) while CMYK colours are suitable for prints.

RGB: 000CD - 17174D - FFFFFFFF

CMYK: 35469D - 1D194C - FFFFFFFF

Complementary Colour

RGB & CMYK

F8CF40

RGB and CMYK: F8CF40

This colour will be used in association with the colours in the logo in designing the visual identity of the project and relevant designs.

Typography

Two fonts have been chosen for the project visuals that will be created:

OPEN SANS

Light

ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ

abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz

1234567890

AfriConEU

Regular

ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ

abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz

1234567890

AfriConEU

Extra Bold

ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ

abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz

1234567890

AfriConEU

MONTSERATT

Regular

ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ

abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz

1234567890

AfriConEU

Classic

ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ

abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz

1234567890

AfriConEU

Semi-Bold

ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ

abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz

1234567890

AfriConEU

Annex 2: Template for Reporting Events

- This template should be sent to Youthmakers Hub by partners after attending/organizing/speaking at any event so dissemination efforts can be tracked
- Still, it is advisable to forewarn us whenever you are attending an event to promote it on our website and social media channels.
- Please, take at least two pictures of the event to display the information on our website.

This template can be found in the MS folder [here](#).

Template for Reporting Events

Title of the event	
Date	DD/MM/YYYY
Location	City, Country
Partner attending	
Description	Include information on type of event, objectives, scope, structure and organizers – as applicable
Type of participation	Organizer / Speaker / Attendant
Main Audience	DIHs, Entrepreneurs, Investors, Policymakers, others
Results/ Outcome	What is the impact of the event on the project? Did it create awareness, encourage involvement, create synergies, strengthen links with public bodies, consolidate exploitation?
Documents or links for further information	Agenda, web, presentation etc.
Link in MS folder with photos	(Upload photos from the event in the shared MS folder, create your own folder for each event here)
Other Comments	

Annex 3: Partners' Communication Channels and Contacts

INOVA+ Innovation Services S.A.

Website	https://inova.business/
Twitter	-
LinkedIn	INOVA+
Facebook	-
Instagram	-
YouTube channel	INOVA SA
Contact person	Ana Solange Leal
Contact e-mail	ana.leal@inova.business

Emerging Communities Africa

Website	https://www.emergingcommunities.africa
Twitter	@emergingtechAF
LinkedIn	Emerging Communities Africa
Facebook	@emergingtechaf
Instagram	emergingtechaf
YouTube channel	Emerging Communities Africa
Contact person	Peace Odili
Contact e-mail	peace.odili@emergingcommunities.africa

Youthmakers Hub

Website	www.youthmakershub.com
Twitter	@youthmakershub
LinkedIn	Youthmakers Hub
Facebook	@youthmakershub
Instagram	youthmkarershub
YouTube channel	Youthmakers Hub
Contact person	Marilena Maragkou
Contact e-mail	info@youthmakershub.com

ASSOCIACAO PORTO BUSINESS SCHOOL (PBS)- U. PORTO

Website	https://www.pbs.up.pt/
Twitter	-
LinkedIn	Porto Business School
Facebook	@portobusinessschool
Instagram	portobusinessschool
YouTube channel	Porto Business School
Contact person	Catarina Reis
Contact e-mail	creis@pbs.up.pt

OUTBOX (U) LIMITED

Website	http://www.outbox.co.ug/
Twitter	Outbox
LinkedIn	Outbox Uganda
Facebook	@OutboxHub
Instagram	outboxhub
YouTube channel	Outbox
Contact person	Perez Apiyo Masinde
Contact e-mail	pmasinde@outbox.co.ug

DPIXEL SRL

Website	https://dpixel.it/
Twitter	@dpixel_vc
LinkedIn	dPixel
Facebook	@dpixelvc
Instagram	-
YouTube channel	-
Contact person	Damelio Lorenzo
Contact e-mail	dameliolorenzo@gmail.com

Stimmuli for Social Change

Website	http://www.stimmuli.eu/
Twitter	@StimmuliFChange
LinkedIn	Stimmuli For Social Change
Facebook	@Stimmuli
Instagram	-
YouTube channel	-
Contact person	Irene Kalemaki
Contact e-mail	irene.kalemaki@stimmuli.eu

ITC - Innovation Technology Cluster Murska Sobota

Website	http://www.itc-cluster.com/
Twitter	@ITC_cluster
LinkedIn	ITC - Innovation Technology Cluster
Facebook	-
Instagram	-
YouTube channel	-
Contact person	Sasa Straus
Contact e-mail	sasa.straus@itc-cluster.com

Buni Innovation Hub

Website	www.bunihub.or.tz
Twitter	@bunihub
LinkedIn	Buni Hub
Facebook	@bunihub
Instagram	bunihub
YouTube channel	Buni Hub
Contact person	Edwin Bakalemwa
Contact e-mail	edwin.bakalemwa@costech.or.tz

Africa Technology Business Network

Website	www.africatbn.com
Twitter	@africatbn
LinkedIn	ATBN
Facebook	@AfricaTBN
Instagram	
YouTube channel	
Contact person	Eunice Baguma Ball
Contact e-mail	eunice@africatbn.com

Hapa Foundation

Website	www.hapaspace.com
Twitter	@hapaSpace
LinkedIn	hapaSpace Collaborative Hub
Facebook	@hapaspace
Instagram	hapaspace
YouTube channel	hapa Space
Contact person	Gideon Brefo
Contact e-mail	gideon@hapaspace.com